

Codebook - Perspectives, Needs and Challenges for Sustainable Software Engineering Teams

Multiple perspectives of sustainability	Balance between environmental-economic-social dimensions		it should be environmental aspect ... cost perspective as well, economical aspect, and then it should be the social aspect as well. So whatever you are trying to do today, it should cover all the features that would be needed later on, and it should be basically seamlessly integrated into the upcoming technologies
	Environmental – Technical concerns	minimal	softwares that are optimized so they use less carbon footprint
		no footprint	things like large-scale deep learning models trained on massive amounts of data using exponentially more data and exponentially more compute and exponentially more power. And then having that power doesn't always come from RENEWABLE SOURCES. It is not sustainable.
		Circular economy	sustainability is reusing or basically you know the circular economy ... you use the stuff and then if it's not usable anymore you kind of reuse the parts, so nothing goes to waste and always donate ... zero wastage for me.
	Political strategy		it's also quite a political topic at the minute sustainability it's something that gets a lot of uh publicity from government organisations
	Social dimension	Employee wellbeing	In a very busy environment... sometimes the workload's not sustainable.
	Survive longer		when we say sustainable just make sure like things have long life
	Environmental-Social-Technical dimensions	cloud	Moving from on-prem to CLOUD_PROVIDER is a kind of sustainability step we are taking ... it's, like, on-demand, we're not always having resources on and utilizing it.
		code reusability	we have a code which is reusable, and then we can reuse by the application development to the extent how common they have things.
		energy consumption	it is about energy consumption. It's about hardware utilization. ... I read that there is more than 20% growing ratio each year. It's a huge amount. It means doubling each two or four years ... even if that is not a big problem now, I can imagine that it could be a really huge problem in 10 or 20 years. So, better to

			deal with the problem ahead of that than to cry once the catastrophe will take place.	
		reuse computer parts	if we have ... computer parts or any broken parts, maybe get those recycled or repair them rather than buying new parts.	
		Code efficiency	improving efficiency, improving performance, using of better solutions, better designs, and better algorithms that leads to better utilization.	
		good SE practices	What surprised me, ... the most of the advices on how to be more green, It's aligned perfectly with a healthy and good engineering practices in software development ... it is win-win. Right now, I can see that it's win-win-win [Better code – Good SE practices – Sustainable]. Three wins, not just two.	
	Data Availability		Your data's crucial for the bank... to sustain your data and make that... readily available for everyone.	
Motivators to incorporate Sustainability	Improved dependency team communications		There's no clarity... when we can start (a project)... sometimes the colleagues are busy, they don't respond on time... we have to chase a lot.	
		Extra workload	lack of documentation	if you are new and you are coming in like I am to this CLOUD stuff, there is not great documentation. It is not really mandated by anybody. So, you struggle, and it is almost like you are left on an island and you have to figure out how the island works every time you move.
			duplicated work	functionality can come from other project, and you actually end up having this application that's duplicated work ... across any large organization there'll be so much duplicated work and so much duplicated compute time that things are effectively running the same task where one of them could be tweaked in such a minor way to run the other
			Manual process	COMPANY is really bad for their deployment practices and how unsustainable they are. you will have people that end up working a lot of extra hours to get things deployed during like a release window because there's so many manual processes ... that's not sustainable at all.
		deadlines	trying to make the deadlines for the project	

		pressure due to last minute changes	our services are very much in demand in the COMPANY and I guess at difficult aspect of our job is that we too often get last minute demand that we're basically told that this has to be done whether it's regulatory or whatever the case may be and then obviously that puts added pressure and strain on the team.
		lack of experienced staff	don't have enough HUMAN resources. So if you have a bigger application, you should have the proper resources ... who have got some good experience working on it. If you take new developers in a project that is so crucial, that will not help.
		No access to online resources	developing in the startup or in your personal machine is very different to working in a bigger organization ... I'm speaking of technical side. Like if you get a ticket and technically, you're working on your machine, you can get everything done very fast. Because you have access to everything. You have all these like external resources, like Chat GPT, et cetera, et cetera. Well, you have YouTube. But in COMPANY ... not allowed to use YouTube. We're not allowed to use a lot of resources because they're just blocked. ... it's taking ages to get them on board. And we're definitely losing a lot of cost savings. It's a cost opportunity that the COMPANY is literally missing out on. Every day where we're not having it, you could decrease our productivity to three times.
	Organisational benefits	Improved contingencies (requirements and deadlines)	if we have an impact assessment where timelines are looking like they're not going to be met, we would gather the relevant teams ... try and collate all of those resources together to identify how high priority it is. if it's high priority, do we need to then look at options to re-point resources that are on other deliveries to try and resolve and meet the timeline, or is there any opportunity for us to have some re-baselining of the timelines? So can we delay, like have we planned early enough so that we have some time in there to delay this release, or if we can look to combine it with another release
		competition with other companies	A lot of banks are moving their data to cloud solutions... So we are keeping up with competitors.

	Data Availability		Data redundancy like having multiple backup services just in case it fails. ... having a primary and a secondary copy of that data and you've maybe got a primary-secondary, primary-secondary, primary-secondary somewhere else as well and so instead of having two large server farms, you've got six or eight large server from a storage arrays
	Streamlined processes	reactive teams over proactive	There are many people, there's around 400 people that work in the DEPARTMENT. The challenges tend to be around, ultimately to be able to move at speed when there's a need for information and data. And when I say speed, I think we as an organization are potentially slightly reactive to our data needs and as an organization, I think we need to make step change to be more proactive. ... It's reactive in nature because the asks become late. We want to become more proactive, but there's still a learning. ... You can provide data really quickly, but you still want to ensure quality because otherwise garbage in, garbage out in terms of what types of reporting will be produced.
		inefficient use of hardware (multiple production environments)	it's really easy for us to go and be like i want 10 servers for this and then really probably one server would be good enough
		Improper agile implementation	we don't have scrum master kind of things ... we don't have a dedicated professional for running this. we should have agile master etc because developer cannot focus on their work as well as running this agile practice. bad coding practices or blind applying agile practices like that, it leads to growing technical debt.
Potential Trade-offs	Departmental profits vs developer workload		it would be a great if there was a good strategy, ... it needs to make financial sense and it needs to not result in doubling of workloads or stuff like that

	Organisational profits vs employee satisfaction	contributor to massive fossil fuel companies	I feel like we're trying to do loads of these environmental things, and we're trying to really cut down on our power, and we're trying to move towards the maybe green sources ..., but at the same time, we are large contributors to massive fossil fuel companies, so it seems there's a bit of juxtaposition between the efforts.
		just a PR	It's PR at the end of the day... you're not going to advertise you're one of the biggest investors in drilling for oil... you're going to say you're investing in clean energy. There are a lot of large organizations that do some sort of greenwashing... planting a tree over here and don't look anywhere else.
	Risk control (E.g., Security vs Sustainability)		I've got to be honest. It's never been marked as a priority in terms of software development. COMPANY1 right now is in a very much a risk and control era. So they're not really focusing on anything else software engineering related other than just avoiding risk and heightening controls.
	Deadline vs Sustainability		There is always that balance between getting the job done quickly versus doing it right in terms of sustainability and future maintenance.
	Efficient code vs Readability		it's always just a question of balance between efficiency and readability of code because while, of course, you want to get it efficient because then you have less power usage and all that, sometimes most efficient code isn't particularly readable, which then ends up just wasting time and energy for just anyone else coming to look at it in the future
	Functionality vs Sustainability		what we're doing, ticks the box, if it carries out the functionality. But are we doing it in an optimal way? I'm not really exposed to any of that since I've been here.
	Technical debt vs Sustainability		Sustainability is definitely something that a company as large as COMPANY should be focusing on. And as a purely technology team, we should be contributing to that. However, ... I do have concerns ... one of my worries would be that we would introduce tech debt just to meet a target and we would then need to go back and resolve that tech debt and remediate any defects or bugs that we've deployed due to trying to introduce efficiencies.

Challenges in integrating SuSE practices	Clients don't care		A lot of the clients... don't care that much unless they've got their own sustainability goals.
	Mindset	accept more workload to please managers	People are more concerned with their manager's opinion... if a director says this has to be done, I'm not sure how many would say no even if our team can't manage that with the workload they have.
		fear of improper implementation	In a regulated industry like financial services, there's already a lot of governance, there's a lot of steps have to be going through just to enable technical work and allow technical work to happen. So, a lot of non-technical work has to happen as well. There could be a danger that if not implemented correctly, the requirement for more sustainable technology practices actually just creates a lot more non-technical work as well, and that slows everything down and makes things ... less cost effective for organizations, or it could be that things are even slower than now ... I think that's a potential downside
	Could add additional costs		this would add definitely more effort on the organization to train people more time, potentially invest more money and ... the people are busy doing their own things ... and now they have this extra thing to learn as well
	Legacy systems		Most of my life is actually spent reading rather than coding... there's so much legacy stuff... security and risk that you always need to take into account.
	Not considered as a priority		I don't think this is a like a goal or something people advocate for now that much. I think it's something like some people have the idea but it's not like a really global or general idea for now
	Disturbance to work life balance		If working in a more sustainable way requires lots of extra processes or extra pieces within your solution, then that could become maybe quite stressful because you're already time bogged, you're already under time pressure, so it might add to that.

	Poor leadership		who do reportees follow? They follow their managers, and their managers follow their managers. That's how we function here. If they don't set a good example, same will be followed.
	Unawareness of sustainability		if we are prioritizing sustainability then it's going to have to come at the expense of something. what that something is I don't know. I'm like aware of a buzzword sustainability... I don't have much knowledge of sustainability in software engineering.
	Time pressure		at the end of the day, the organization would like their people to be productive and having these kind of extra tasks to their employees and probably their employees are already busy enough, I think this would be a challenge for all for the organization to organize such initiatives in a way that fits in the employees capacity.
Dedicated Sustainability Team	Delegated ownership as a benefit		there should be someone who's taking ownership of this. That's separate team ... because if there isn't, it's never going to happen
	Parallel with security team		people won't be used to developing sustainably initially. It's not necessarily a natural thing. So if you're going to set out those guidance and those policies, you should have some people that people can come and ask questions to ... So we already have that for security, right? We've got the central security team.
	Knowledgeable leadership		Nobody knows exactly how we would be sustainable in software engineering. That would need a dedicated team to look at what we do now, look at the gaps, identify solutions to those gaps and then be in charge of not just implementing but communicating that to people.
	Less workload for the middle managers		If you said to me along with my job, you're supposed to look out for ways in which we can be more environmentally friendly in our software engineering, that's never going to happen because it's, you know, it's just, it needs to be somebody that would need to get really deep into it.

	Difficulties to put into practice		security has the risk which sustainability doesn't have. like you probably lose money if you're not security but you can't really leverage how much you lose if you're not sustainable
	May not drive large workforce		A central team could enable the understanding ... But would they be able to drive it? Not fully, it would have to be individuals within teams to almost be the SME or the expert within each area to make it happen.
	Poor leadership can add new challenges		If you have a diverse culture in the team, you definitely need good leadership. And I have had different managers, and I know this from my personal experience, that leadership skills are very important in order to drive the work. There are people who drive the work, and there are people who analyze the work better, different skills again. You need to see who you are putting up to the leadership, I mean, to the lead role.
Migration to the Cloud as a sustainability solution	Good data redundancy techniques		The reason why we have two backups is we need disaster recovery. So if something goes wrong with production, you have a backup copy of the data. And that's crucial, because if you lose the data and you have nowhere else to get that backed up from ... By having it on cloud, we don't actually have to duplicate the data, because technically the disaster recovery is on your availability zones
	Optimised infrastructure	less infrastructure on premise	it doesn't really matter what cloud platform you use, not only is it more easy for us to access and distribute the data, but it makes you, obviously, more sustainable as well. Because ... we don't now own the infrastructure. We own the data.
		no need for maintenance of hardware	the maintenance side of things when we're now moving towards like fully managed cloud services, it's no longer our responsibility.
		easy to scale and flexible	when there's low peak then we have less resources and where it's anticipated more we can just scale it, that flexibility is allowed with the cloud whereas when we are on prem it's like always on or off. exactly it's always on.

	low employee training costs and wider talent pool as organisational benefit		Cloud is also increasing efficiencies in terms of being able to access human resources, like quite a lot of graduates that we have at the moment have experience in cloud solutions and have experience in that development, so we would have greater access to the resource pool and require less training.
	Pushes developers to be sustainable		if I'm pulling data down from the current on-prem estate, I might say, pull me all the data back every day ... or I'm taking one component part, junking the rest of it and using that data. That's bad habits. When you do that in cloud, you're going to pay for that every day. You're pulling back a billion dollars of data. ... If you only need a component part of that data, write your query to pull back the data you need rather than all the data
	Helps in developer personal growth		a lot more insight into virtualization and containerization